

Development and Testing of an Omni-directional Soft Pneumatic Actuator for Endoscopy

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Abstract—Soft pneumatic actuators are appropriate for operation in unstructured environments because of their adaptability, cost-effectiveness, safety and ease of use. This paper presents the development and testing of an externally reinforced actuator with three independent chambers. Numerical simulations were used to design the actuator and to validate its workability for endoscopy. Finally, experimental tests on the prototype validated the numerical results and characterized the workspace of the actuator.

Keywords—soft robotics, soft pneumatic actuator, omnidirectional, externally reinforced, endoscopy

I. INTRODUCTION

The use of soft robots is growing in different fields, such as in industry for grippers [1], in biomimicry with reproduction of anthropomorphic hands [2] or animal parts [3,4], and in biomedical with exoskeletons and actuators for minimally invasive surgery [5]. Soft pneumatic actuators (SPAs) are becoming increasingly popular for their adaptability, cost-effectiveness, safety and ease of use.

Generally, SPAs flex only in one plane [6,7], adjusting the bending angles by feeding pressure. Omnidirectionality can be achieved by multi-chamber actuation. SPAs with three [8] or more chambers [9] have been proposed recently. Devices of this type can be used in endoscopic analysis to explore inside pipes, tanks or places where hazardous substances are present. These actuators have limitations due to little bending and radial expansion that changes their nominal dimensions.

In this paper, a SPA for endoscopy is presented. The actuator consists of a silicone rubber inner tube and a thermoplastic polyurethane external reinforcement. Silicone rubber was chosen as a suitable material to achieve the highest value of bending angle and the largest possible working area. The inner tube contains three radial 120° pneumatic chambers, as well as the central housing for the endoscope and two smaller housings for two robot arms. The endoscope can be used to explore the environment, and the two robot arms can interact with it, such as picking up small objects. Reinforcement limits radial expansion and maximizes bending. Numerical simulations were used to validate preliminarily the omnidirectionality of the actuator. The pressure in each chamber is independently managed with a pressure-proportional solenoid valve. The bending plane and its magnitude can be managed with each triplet of pressure. Finally, experimental tests validated numerical simulations and characterized the workspace of the actuator.

Section 2 presents the design and manufacturing process of the prototype. In Section 3 there are numerical simulations and the experimental results. Section 4 concludes the paper with future improvements.

II. DESIGN AND MANUFACTURING PROCESS

The designed SPA is composed of an inner tube, an external reinforcement and a connector.

The tube is made of R PRO20 silicone rubber by injection into PLA molds. The latter were printed to reproduce in negative the geometry of the same tube. Three holes are inside the tube, one for the endoscopic and the other two can be used to place robot arms. The geometry of the chambers is maximized, always providing a 1.5 mm thickness of silicone with both the inner holes and outer surface. This promotes the fluidity of the silicone by avoiding turbulence that would result in air inclusions or inadequate mold fills. The left end in Fig. 1a is closed, while the right end is open to position the connector.

The external reinforcement was made by an i-fast QIDI 3D printer, and it is reported in Fig. 1b. The adopted printed parameters are the same as used in previous work [10]. The 36 cuts (12 per chamber) on the reinforcement act as virtual hinges. In addition, there are connections between the various cuts (circled in red in Fig.1b) to give geometric references, ensuring a connection without stiffening the structure. The outer diameter, inner diameter, holes for endoscope and robot arms were fixed at, 34, 30, 6 and 4 mm, respectively.

The connector in Fig.1c was made by SLA and it ensures the airflow from valves to chambers. The three threaded holes are for attaching the three M5 pneumatic fittings. Instead, the three connections of length 14.5 mm fit inside the right end of the tube and are fixed with super glue to prevent air leakage.

Fig. 1. Details of SPA components: (a) inner tube; (b) external reinforcement; (c) connector. (d) Assembly scheme with an endoscope and two robot arms.

III. NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS AND TESTING

The need for numerical modeling depends on the strong nonlinearities of the actuator due to the nonlinear behavior of compressed air, friction with reinforcement, large deformations, and the nonlinear constitutive law of silicone rubber. Each geometry was created in Solid Edge 2024 and exported to Ansys Workbench 2023 R2. The following common settings were adopted in all numerical models: automatic meshing with elements smaller than 1.5 mm; tetrahedral elements for all components; a fixed constraint at one end of the air inlet/outlet port; a pressure ramp in the range 0-1.2 bar acting on the inner surfaces of the silicone rubber; effect of gravitational force; frictional contact constraints, based on the penalty stiffness method and with a friction coefficient of 0.5, between the elements of the reinforcing structure and the inner tube; constrained contact constraints between the AEs and DVHs elements; nonlinear analysis using the Newton-Raphson method; large strain algorithm; auto time stepping, program-controlled. The mechanical behavior of R PRO20 was modeled by the 2-order Yeoh, $C_{10}=0.0734$ MPa, $C_{20}=0.0068$ MPa, $D_1=D_2=0.0$ MPa⁻¹. TPU was modeled as an isotropic elastic material with a Young modulus of 50 MPa and a Poisson ratio equal to 0.4. Fig. 2a shows the deformation state with the three chambers at 0.2, 1.2 and 1.0 bar, respectively, and Fig. 2b only with chamber 2 at 1.2 bar.

After verifying the functionality of the SPA, a test bench (Fig. 3a) was made for the realized prototype. First, two Logitech HD1080p cameras were calibrated in MATLAB Calibration Toolbox. The two cameras were placed one on the frontal plane and one on the top. A red marker (Fig. 2b-c) was mounted on the top of the SPA to easily identify the tip position. Lens distortion errors were corrected with the camera parameters, and it was possible to trace the marker's pixel coordinates back to its positions in mm. The three proportional pressure solenoid valves are managed using software developed in LabVIEW 2021.

Specifically, the desired pressure values are set, and based on the characteristics of the valves, the necessary control voltages are applied. An extensive test campaign was conducted by measuring the marker position for both single-chamber pressurizations and pressure combinations in the three chambers. The workspaces recorded in the X-Y and X-Z planes are shown in Fig. 3d-e, respectively.

Fig. 2. Deformation states in numerical simulation with: (a) $P_1=0.2$ bar, $P_2=1.2$ bar e $P_3=1.0$ bar; (b) $P_1=0.0$ bar, $P_2=1.2$ bar e $P_3=0.0$ bar.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, a new SPA for endoscopic applications was presented. The three-chamber architecture made it possible to achieve omnidirectionality. It was possible to maximize the working space of the actuator thanks to the external TPU reinforcement to limit radial expansion, maximizing the bending angles. In the future, a simple and effective interface will be developed to manage the movement of the actuator and the characterization of the workspace with different orientations of the same.

Fig. 3. Experimental characterization: (a) test bench; (b) identification of marker position by the two cameras; (c) deformation states with only one chamber pressurized to 1.2 bar; (d) workspace in X-Y plane; (e) workspace in X-Z plane.

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